

ISic0817

I.Sicily inscription 0817

Language

Latin

Type

building

Material

limestone

(Trapani)

Object

slab

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

Metcalfe 2015.11.12

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lilybaeum

Place of origin (modern)

Marsala

Provenance

excavations in Roman villa in Marsala

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Marsala, Museo

archeologico regionale Lilibeo Marsala - Baglio Anselmi

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: EDR074416

0. [---]

1. opere plataeam plateam vici Se p [tizodi]

2. lapide Drepanitano sua p (ecunia) strav (it) ;

3. Q (uintus) Fabius Q (uinti) f (ilius) Maec (ia) Caesilius

4. Modius Titianus, q (uaestor) pro pr (aetore)

5. prov (inciae) Sici (liae) , plataeam plateam vici

6. Septizodi sternendam et

7. perficiendam curavit ded [i]

8. cavitque.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 175811

EDR 074416

EDCS 12800324

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 1964.0182

Barbieri, G. 1961. Nuove iscrizioni di Marsala. *Kokalos*. 7: 15-52. At no.2

Manganaro, G. 1988. La Sicilia da Sesto Pompeo a Diocleziano. *ANRW*. 2.11.1: 3-89. At 45

Licensed under a Creative

Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-22): ISic0817. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4385321>

Photo M. Metcalfe